

1 North York Moors Array (NYMAR) for enhancing regional background monitoring of
2 Southern North Sea CO₂ storage sites

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35 **Abstract**

36 Measurement of earthquake signals is a key component to the monitoring of geological CO₂
37 storage projects. Beamforming methods using dense seismic arrays have recently been
38 employed in the baseline monitoring of CO₂ storage projects in the Northern North Sea. To
39 further test the efficacy of arrays for regional earthquake monitoring, a seismic array was
40 deployed on the North York Moors, northeast England, UK, broadly targeting the Southern
41 North Sea, a region where CO₂ storage projects are planned but monitoring remains limited.
42 The North York Moors Array (NYMAR) has been operating since September 2023, streaming
43 data to the University of Oxford for interim storage and processing. Its location was a
44 compromise between distance to the primary monitoring target – the Endurance carbon storage
45 licence area – and several factors, including site conditions, presumed noise levels, and land
46 ownership and permissions. Characterisation work has found the site well-suited to the
47 beamforming methods being used, with thin superficial deposits and a relatively low-noise
48 environment. Preliminary beamforming analysis shows an improvement over the baseline
49 detection capability of the UK national seismic network of around half a magnitude unit.
50 Continuous data from the first year of the deployment is available through the UK National
51 Geoscience Data Centre.

52 **1 Introduction**

53 Carbon dioxide (CO₂) storage projects are currently underway in the North Sea. While the
54 region is generally considered to have low seismic hazard (Bungum et al., 1991), it is
55 nevertheless essential to evaluate the frequency and magnitude of local earthquakes during the
56 development of these operations (e.g., Verdon et al., 2011; Zoback & Gorelick, 2012; Goertz-
57 Allmann et al., 2014). Seismicity can delineate the location of faults and other pre-existing
58 structures (e.g., dominant fracture trends) near prospective storage sites, some of which could
59 act as hydraulic conduits for CO₂ migration (e.g., Gholami et al., 2024). The faulting style of

60 seismic events also directly relates to the in-situ stresses, which can help in constraining the
61 state of stress at potential storage sites. Stress measurements inferred from faulting style (i.e.,
62 stress inversion) can be combined with the results of borehole stress indicators and
63 measurements, and other seismological methods, such as stress drop (e.g., Abercombie, 2021)
64 or seismic anisotropy analysis (e.g., Teanby et al., 2004) to provide a more robust and complete
65 assessment of the regional and local state of stress, aiding in both the characterising and
66 operating storage reservoirs.

67 The risk of injection-induced seismicity is also present for these operations (e.g., Vilarrasa et
68 al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2023). Both operators and regulators therefore require a clear
69 understanding of the rate of natural seismicity, to identify and distinguish induced events, and
70 to assess the likelihood of induced fault reactivation. This requires sufficient background
71 earthquake monitoring, with detection rates and location uncertainty low enough to identify
72 any faulting which could affect the CO₂ storage complex.

73 However, the detection and location of seismicity in offshore regions is limited by the lack of
74 near-field seismic stations. The UK's Southern North Sea, where many CO₂ storage projects
75 are being developed (see **Figure 1**), faces this issue. The first project being developed – the
76 Endurance storage project (highlighted in **Figure 1** and Figure 2) – has an approximate
77 detection capability with the UK national seismic network estimated to be around $M \sim 2$ (see
78 Galloway et al., 2024). Offshore sensors (such as ocean-bottom seismometers, ocean-bottom
79 nodes, or offshore surface fibre optic cables) could be deployed to remedy this issue. However,
80 the sensor and deployment costs are generally higher, and these systems do not typically supply
81 real-time data. Offshore systems can also be affected by timing, response, and coupling issues
82 detrimentally affecting signal quality (e.g., Loviknes et al., 2020; Zarifi et al., 2023).

83

84 **Figure 1.** Location of the North York Moors Array at three scales. (a) A national overview, where the
 85 central station of the array (NYM1) shown as a red triangle, and the black polygons show CO₂ storage
 86 licence block areas (NSTA, 2024). The red rectangle shows the area shown in (b), whilst the red polygon
 87 highlights the license block of the Endurance storage project, the primary monitoring target of the study.
 88 (b) A regional overview in northeast England, with (b) the area shown in (c) as a red rectangle, and the
 89 nearby UK national seismic network station in Glaisdale, North Yorkshire (GDLE), referred to in
 90 Section 4, as a yellow triangle. (c) A local view, with each station in the array shown as a red triangle.

91 In contrast, onshore array methods may allow for improved signal detection and location in
 92 offshore regions, without these deficits of offshore instrumentation. Zarifi et al. (2023)

93 demonstrated that a dense seismic array provided significant improvement to the detection (of
94 around 1 magnitude unit) and location of offshore earthquakes in the Northern North Sea.
95 Further test cases are required, however, to know exactly the level of improvement onshore
96 arrays may provide in each geographical region, with different near surface conditions, regional
97 geology, and geometries of pre-existing seismic networks. This additional assessment is
98 needed to determine if arrays are a widely applicable, cost-effective monitoring tool for CO₂
99 storage operators and regulators.

100 Here, the deployment of the North York Moors seismic array (NYMAR) aims to improve
101 detection of seismicity in the Southern North Sea using frequency-wavenumber beamforming
102 on continuous waveform data recorded by the array (e.g., Schweitzer et al., 2012). This study
103 summarises the deployment and initial performance assessment of an onshore seismic array on
104 the North York Moors, northeastern England (location shown in Figure 1)..

105 **2 Deployment description**

106 As in Zarifi et al. (2023), the objective of the dense array deployment is to improve detection
107 capability of seismicity. In this case, this is for the Southern North Sea region around
108 burgeoning CO₂ storage project areas, principally the Endurance storage license block. For this,
109 several factors are considered, including array geometry design, location and near surface
110 conditions, and access to data connections. These are discussed in the following sections.

111 *2.1 Array design*

112 Optimal array design maximises the number of interstation distances as this determines how
113 sensitive the array is to frequencies of interest (see Schweitzer et al., 2012). This results in the
114 aperture of the array broadly controlling the slowness resolution for small wavelengths – larger
115 aperture arrays are more sensitive to smaller wavenumbers (i.e., slownesses). This means the
116 upper limit of wavelengths (λ) suitable for beamforming is around the aperture (a) of the array

117 (i.e., the largest interstation distance), where the array will function like a single station for λ
118 $\gg a$. The station geometry of NYMAR is shown in **Figure 1**.

119 Given NYMAR's aperture of 1 km and the approximate near surface velocity structure, its
120 lower limit of sensitivity is to signals of around 2 Hz. The minimum interstation distances
121 define the maximum frequency the array is sensitive to, which for NYMAR is around 15 Hz.
122 Being sensitive in these frequencies is suitable for improving detection of smaller magnitude,
123 local earthquakes.

124 A greater number of array elements helps to increase the number of different interstation
125 distances, thus improving slowness resolution. NYMAR's eight-element design was a
126 compromise between performance and cost. The approximate locations of each sensor were
127 chosen in advance of deployment, using two concentric rings surrounding a central station.
128 Potential station locations were simulated by rotating the inner ring to find the best locations
129 which avoid radial alignment and maximise the number of interstation distances. This resulted
130 in a slight radial offset of the inner ring relative to the outer ring. The radii of the rings were
131 chosen using Equation 9.25 of Schweitzer et al. (2012).

132 *2.2 Siting*

133 Another important consideration for siting is the near-surface conditions (i.e., the shallow
134 velocity structure). Relatively hard rock sites are required, where the superficial deposits are
135 sufficiently thin. This is to stop the incidence angles of the signals being rotated vertically by
136 slow velocity layers in the shallow subsurface. Due to the prospective nature of the study, a
137 site with hard rock as close to the surface as possible is required. In the onshore area closest to
138 the CO₂ operations in the Southern North Sea, the upland areas of the North York Moors, away
139 from valleys containing thick peat deposits, meet this criterion (**Figure 2**). The shallow depth

140 of the superficial deposits at the eventual site was verified via a seismic refraction survey, as
141 discussed in Section 3.1 below.

142
143 **Figure 2.** Maximum superficial deposit thickness map for the northeast coast of England, UK. This
144 uses data from the BGS Superficial Deposit Thickness (1 km hex-grid) dataset (Lawley, 2016). The red
145 dashed rectangle highlights the area surrounding the North York Moors National Park, the chosen
146 deployment site of NYMAR. Carbon storage licence blocks are shown as red polygons, using data from
147 the North Sea Transition Authority (NSTA, 2024). The red polygon highlights the license block of the
148 Endurance storage project, the primary monitoring target of the study. Coordinates are British National
149 Grid.

150 When siting, there is a compromise between distance from the monitoring target, site and noise
151 conditions, land use, and land ownership. The North York Moors were also chosen due to their
152 relatively quiet environs, with large areas of land owned by a single party, agency, or authority,
153 far from population centres and roads. The site used for NYMAR is owned and operated by
154 the UK Ministry of Defence and is managed as a part of the Royal Air Force base Fylingdales.
155 This land is over 1.5 km from the nearest road and approximately 3 km from buildings or other
156 infrastructure (see **Figure 1**). The single landowner made securing permissions easier than

157 spreading the array across several parcels of land, which was deemed to be more likely if the
158 array were in the Vale of Pickering to the south of the North York Moors (i.e., closer to the
159 monitoring target, the Endurance storage project). However, the chosen site is located within a
160 Site of Special Scientific Interest within the North York Moors national park, and thus further
161 permissions were needed from Natural England to deploy the instruments. These were secured
162 as seismometer deployments have a low environmental impact (only affecting ~ 1 m² of land).
163 This choice, however, did increase the administrative burden required to site the seismometers
164 and remains in the maintenance of the array.

165 *2.3 Instrumentation*

166 NYMAR consists of eight Gralp Certimus broadband seismometers over a circular area with
167 a diameter of 1 km recording at 200 Hz. They have low power demand, with a maximum draw
168 of ~ 1 W, making them suitable for solar-powered deployments. Their design allows for
169 accurate ground motion recording at any deployment angle (i.e., tilt), with a relatively low
170 instrument self-noise. This facilitated the use of direct burial as the deployment method for
171 NYMAR's seismometers. Sensors were buried in pits around 0.5 to 1 m deep. Two 115 W
172 solar panels charge a 160 Ahr battery bank, which enables the instruments to be continuously
173 powered through the darker winter months.

174 *2.4 Telemetry*

175 NYMAR is telemetered, with each sensor connected to a Teltonika RUT 955 modem equipped
176 with a 4G SIM. The power system was designed to facilitate the ~ 6 W of power draw that this
177 telemetry requires. The RUT 955 modems (hereafter modems) are configured to automatically
178 connect to the 4G telecommunications network and to join a virtual private network (VPN)
179 providing an encrypted connection and static IP address, which allows for secure remote
180 connections. The modems act as the router for an ethernet network local to each site with access

181 to the modem configuration possible via the VPN permitting remote network administration
182 and monitoring. The modem firewalls are configured to block all incoming internet traffic
183 which does not originate from the VPN. The modems are configured with port forwarding from
184 the external VPN interface to the Certimus to allow HTTP requests, used to view the instrument
185 status page and request data. This arrangement also allows console access for remote
186 debugging and remote procedure calls required to make the instruments visible in Güralp's
187 Discovery software. Real-time telemetry also allows for continual monitoring of instrument
188 health, allowing for rapid instrument servicing in response to faults. Each stations generates
189 approximately 73 Mb of three-component data per day, or 2.2Gb per month, depending on
190 noise levels which is well within the 10Gb per month data allowance on the 4G SIMs which
191 gives headroom for data backfilling. Data is pulled from the array daily to a cloud-based service
192 connected to the VPN and is then retrieved for secure storage and processing on high
193 performance computing facilities at the University of Oxford. This automated data collection
194 pulls data for the preceding two days, to ensure data completeness, with the data transfer taking
195 between 5 and 10 minutes.

196 **3 Data and results**

197

198 **Figure 3.** Summary plot of continuous waveforms data available for the NYMAR stations for the first
199 year of the deployments (September 30th, 2023, to September 30th, 2024) Vertical blue bars show data
200 overlaps, with vertical red bars showing data gaps. Note that the data has been collected from the
201 instruments at both hourly and daily intervals, which causes the varying frequency of overlaps. See text
202 for explanation of various data gaps. Figure generated using obspy-scan (Krischer et al., 2015).

203 Three-component continuous waveform data have been collected for the eight stations since
204 October 1st, 2023, and it is planned that the instruments will continue to record data until
205 August 2026. All waveform data is recorded at a sample frequency of 200 Hz. The data

206 completeness for the first year of recording is summarised in Figure 3. Collected continuous
207 data for the first year of recording has been provided to the National Geoscience Data Centre
208 (NGDC) operated by the British Geological Survey (BGS) on behalf of the UK National
209 Environmental Research Council (NERC). This is available at the DOI: **NGDC DOI TBC AS**
210 **OF SEPT 2025**. The FDSN network code 3N has been minted (Asplet et al., 2023) for
211 deposition of the complete dataset onto Earthscope.

212 Data is collected remotely using the previously described telemetry and is also downloaded
213 from the stations during servicing where required. There is a short data gap between January
214 1st and January 4th, 2024, for all stations in the array due to a lack of power supply from the
215 solar panels, in a time where only a single battery and solar panel were at each site. All stations
216 resumed recording from January 5th, 2024, when weather conditions improved. For the first
217 year of operation, the data availability is greater than 95% (Figure 3), except for NYM6. On
218 18th July 2024, power was lost to NYM6 due to flooding. The station was repaired on 8th
219 August 2024, creating a data gap of approximately 21 days.

220 *3.1 Near surface characterisation*

221 To test the depth of the superficial deposits at the chosen site, a small seismic refraction study
222 was conducted using the central station of the array, NYM1. Hammer shots were conducted at
223 1 m, 2 m, and 5 m intervals up to 50 m from the station, with a closer shot spacing used nearest
224 the station to capture the cross over point between the direct and refracted arrivals. Four
225 separate lines were acquired, which radiated out from the station in the cardinal directions.
226 These were design to assess the refractor geometry and the presence of dipping boundaries. By
227 measuring the first arrivals from these hammer shots, we determine the velocity profile and
228 approximate depth of the shallow bedrock at the site. An example seismic section is shown in
229 Figure 4, which shows a subtle P-wave first arrival within the initial 0.05s of the shot gather,

230 followed by a dispersive, low frequency Rayleigh wave. For all four lines we measure P-wave
231 velocities of 300 ms^{-1} and 3000 ms^{-1} for the direct and refracted arrivals respectively, which
232 indicates a planar interface immediate below the station. A simplified two-layer model is then
233 applied to measure the depth of the low velocity superficial deposits. The cross-over distance
234 in the first arrivals indicates a thickness of approximately 2 m, corroborating the regional
235 superficial deposit thickness maps used in the siting of the array. This thin layer of the slower
236 near surface layers is far below the wavelengths of signals of interest for regional earthquakes
237 and thus are not likely to affect the inclinations of the arrivals at the array.

238
239 **Figure 4.** An example seismic section from the refraction survey conducted at the central station of the
240 array NYM1. The section shows subtle P-wave first arrivals followed by low frequency dispersive
241 Rayleigh waves. Red dashed show the linear fits through the picked first arrivals with measured
242 velocities of 300 ms^{-1} and 3000 ms^{-1} . The intersection point of the direct and head wave arrivals can be
243 used to find the depth to more consolidated material.

244 4 Preliminary observations

245 4.1 Noise

246

247 **Figure 5.** Probabilistic power spectral density calculated for vertical component (HHZ) data from each
248 station in the North York Moors array, where signal amplitude is plotted as a function of frequency, for
249 data from 29th September 2023 to 29th September 2024. White dashed lines show the 5 and 95
250 percentiles, and dark grey solid lines show the reference high and low noise models for seismic stations
251 (Peterson, 1993). The orange line shows a reference spectra for a M_L 1.5 earthquake at a hypocentral
252 distance of 100 km (Clinton and Heaton, 2002).

253 Figure 5 shows probabilistic power density spectra (PPSD) calculated using the vertical
254 components (HHZ) for each station in the array. The station PPSDs are calculated for a 12-
255 month time span, from 29th September 2023 to 29th September 2024, following the routines of
256 McNamara and Buland (2004) as implemented in Obspy (Krischer et al., 2015). In the
257 frequency range of primary interest (2-10 Hz for small earthquakes), each station's noise levels
258 perform well and are below Peterson (1993)'s high noise model. Most stations have a median
259 noise amplitude of around 20 dB lower than a reference spectrum for a M_L 1.5 earthquake at
260 100 km distance (Figure 5; Clinton and Heaton, 2002). PPSDs for the two horizontal

261 components can be found in the supplementary material (Supplementary Figure 1 and
262 Supplementary Figure 2).

263
264 **Figure 6.** Probabilistic power density spectra for vertical, north and east components of GDLE, the
265 closest station in the UK permanent seismic network (GB) to NYMAR. White dashed lines show the 5
266 and 95 percentiles, dark grey solid lines show the reference high and low noise models for seismic
267 stations (Peterson, 1993). The orange line shows a reference spectra for a M_L 1.5 earthquake at a
268 hypocentral distance of 100 km (Clinton and Heaton, 2002).

269 When compared to the noise levels at the nearest station in the UK permanent seismic network
270 (GDLE; location shown in Figure 1, PPSD in Figure 6), noise levels are higher across
271 NYMAR. Noise levels on all three components are at least 5-10 dB higher than GDLE in the
272 frequency range of interest and are significantly higher for lower frequencies. This reflects
273 differences in the noise field, site conditions, and the temporary, lower quality, nature of the
274 deployment. The initial planned lifespan of NYMAR was one year due to funding and
275 permissions restrictions, restricting the use of vaults. This lifespan has now been extended, and
276 the array is currently planned to remain active until August 2026. Deployment restrictions also
277 meant that fully worked vaults or shallow boreholes were not permissible deployment options.
278 It is likely that a significant improvement in noise levels in the 2 to 10 Hz frequency range

279 could be achieved if the deployment was permanent, with the sensors vaulted (e.g., Antony et
280 al., 2020; discussion of Antony et al., 2022).

281

282 Figure 7. Photos of the typical deployment conditions for NYMAR stations. (a) shows NYM8 prior to
283 the installation of the 2nd solar panel and the telemetry system. The hole for the seismometer can be
284 seen ~2 m in front of the wooden solar panel frame, with power, GPS, and data cables buried to frame.
285 The batteries and solar power regulator are buried in a waterproof enclosure directly in front of the solar
286 panel. (b) shows the complete power and telemetry system for NYM3 along with its surroundings.
287 Heather surrounds this station, at around ~0.3 m high. This station could not be relocated into a patch
288 of clear ground without significantly altering the array geometry.

289 The detrimental effect on the noise of the temporary nature of the deployment can be most
290 clearly seen for station NYM4 (Figure 5). This station is the noisiest in the array due to its
291 individual site conditions. The site for NYM4 is covered by a large area of heather and gorse,
292 up to 1 m in height. This vegetation acts to significantly increase high frequency noise at the
293 station in high winds, increasing the 95-percentile noise level to above the Peterson (1993) high
294 noise model for part of our targeted frequency range (2 - 10 Hz). Due to restrictions in the
295 management of the land, it was not possible to clear vegetation surrounding the stations.
296 Clearing thick vegetation in the surrounding area of the stations would improve the noise levels

297 at all stations, particularly NYM4. The design of the array geometry also limited the scope to
298 move stations more than ~10 m from the proposed site without affecting the performance of
299 the array. This forced stations, such as NYM4, to be deployed in sub-optimal sites amongst the
300 thicker vegetation. An example of the site conditions is shown in Figure 7.

301 Future work, with expanded permissions acquired to service and upgrade NYMAR, could
302 significantly improve the noise performance. The construction of vaults or drilling of shallow
303 boreholes would likely not impact the land any more significantly than the existing
304 deployment. These permissions were not sought for this study due to time and cost constraints.

305 *4.2 Detections*

306 All waveform data recorded between October 1st, 2023, and June 30th, 2024, has been processed
307 using the cross-correlation f-k beamforming method adapted from Hudson et al. (2023). To
308 identify potential earthquakes in the beam power time series, a median absolute deviation
309 (MAD) detector is used where peaks in the beam power time series for vertical, $P_Z(t)$, and
310 horizontal, $P_H(t)$, components greater than a chosen MAD multiplier of 4 and a minimum
311 event separation time of 5 seconds are considered potential P and S phase picks respectively.
312 The beam power time series are processed in hour-long chunks, with the median of each hour
313 used to detect triggers.

314 A limitation of the MAD method is that the multiplier must be optimised for the data yet for
315 such a large continuous dataset, where the amplitude of the beam power traces varies depending
316 on the noise levels at the array, the optimum MAD multiplier will vary across the dataset which
317 is a challenge for automated data processing. Future work is planned to explore implementing
318 more appropriate detectors, such as a generalised F detector (Selby, 2008), which gives the
319 probability of a detected signal being a coherent seismic phase arriving at the array.

320

321 **Figure 8.** Local magnitude of earthquakes reported in the British Geological Survey catalogue during
 322 the first 9 months (1st October 2023 - 30th June 2024) of the NYMAR deployment, plotted as a function
 323 of hypocentral distance from the array (grey circles). Manually selected earthquakes which are detected
 324 by the array are shown by the blue stars, whilst earthquakes which are not detected are shown by the
 325 red crosses. Two example events, a M_L 2.2 earthquake which occurred in the Southern North Sea on
 326 June 30th, 2024, at 06:42:17.8 UTC (yellow) and a M_L 1.0 earthquake that occurred near the village of
 327 Kilnsey, Yorkshire on April 10th, 2024, at 04:36:378.4 UTC (pink), are highlighted.

328 Work to analyse the beamforming results is still ongoing, and no analysis in this report is
 329 conducted to detect earthquakes with NYMAR that are not already included in the British
 330 Geological Survey (BGS) earthquake catalogue. Here, we use the British Geological Survey
 331 earthquake catalogue to calibrate the performance of the array. During the first nine months of
 332 the deployment, 203 earthquakes were recorded by the BGS across the UK. To identify
 333 earthquakes with a reasonable likelihood of detection, we invert the UK local magnitude scale

334 (Luckett et al., 2019) to screen events for which the expected amplitude at NYMAR would
335 give a signal-to-noise ratio greater than 1. Noise amplitudes for NYMAR are estimated for a
336 one octave range centred on 5 Hz and are converted to displacement following Möllhoff et al.
337 (2019). To incorporate the improvement in signal-to-noise ratio from array analysis we take
338 the median noise amplitude divided by \sqrt{N} , where N is the number of stations in the array,
339 giving a noise displacement estimate of 1.98 nm. Using this we can calculate detectable M_L as
340 a function of hypocentral distance from NYMAR (Figure 8). This model identifies 49
341 earthquakes which were likely to be detectable at the array. Data recorded by NYMAR for
342 these earthquakes were beamformed, with the beam traces manually inspected for a detection.
343 An additional 7 significant events with an expected signal-to-noise ratio less than 1 were also
344 reviewed, bringing the total number of earthquakes which were manually beamformed and
345 inspected to 56 (Figure 8).

346 For each earthquake, 2 to 5 minute sections are extracted from the raw seismograms and are
347 pre-processed to correct for instrument response, a linear trend, and the raw data mean. The
348 data is bandpass filtered with corner frequencies of 2 and 10 Hz before the cross-correlation f-
349 k beamforming is applied. F-k beamforming is performed in the frequency domain with 50
350 frequency samples, 200 backazimuth samples in the range 0 - 360° and 80 horizontal slowness
351 samples in the range 0 - 0.8 sm^{-1} . The output time series of beam power and backazimuth are
352 inspected with the previously described MAD detector used to identify P and S arrivals.

353

354 **Figure 9.** Example of the beamforming outputs $P(t)$, $\theta(t)$, and $u(t)$ for a M_L 2.2 earthquake which
 355 occurred in the Southern North Sea on June 30th, 2024, at 06:42:17.8 UTC. P and S phase picks are
 356 made using an automated median absolute deviation (MAD) trigger.

357 **Figure 9** shows an example of the beam power, backazimuth and slowness time series for a
 358 M_L 2.2 earthquake which occurred in the Southern North Sea on June 30th, 2024, at 06:42:17.8
 359 UTC (Galloway, 2025). This example shows characteristic clear spikes in the beam power time
 360 series on the horizontal and vertical components for P and S arrivals and a corresponding
 361 consistent backazimuth and slowness. For prospective detections the picked P and S arrivals,
 362 and the corresponding back azimuth and slowness, are used to form beam seismograms using
 363 phase-weighted stacking (Schimmel and Paulssen, 1997). This beam seismogram is then
 364 inspected to confirm P and S picks (e.g., **Figure 10**), only if a clear P and S arrival is evident
 365 in the earthquake considered to be detected by the array.

366

367 **Figure 10.** Beam seismogram for the event shown in Figure 9. Beam is formed by performing phase-
 368 weighted stacking (Schimmel and Paulssen, 1997), with $n=1$, for the backazimuth and slowness of the
 369 picked P and S phases.

370 Following this inspection, 25 of the 56 reviewed earthquakes are detected by the array (Figure
 371 8). The smallest magnitude earthquake detected by NYMAR is a M_L 1.0 earthquake which
 372 occurred near Kilnsey, North Yorkshire on April 10th, 2024, at 04:36:37.0 UTC (Galloway,
 373 2025). Despite the event occurring nearly 100 km away from the array the event is clearly
 374 resolved by the f-k beamforming, with clear P and S arrivals formed in the phase-weight stack
 375 beam seismogram (Supplementary Figure 3). Figure 8 shows that there is some variability in
 376 detectability where events at similar hypocentral distances are both detected and not detected.
 377 There are also notable missed earthquakes, such as the Marth 13th 2024 M_L 2.0 earthquake
 378 which occurred at 14:49:48.2 UTC nearby Swaby, Lincolnshire (Galloway, 2025),
 379 approximately 134 km from NYMAR. The detectability of individual earthquakes is dependent

380 on noise levels at the array on a given day and the earthquake focal mechanism, as the array
381 only samples one point of the focal sphere. The Kilnsey earthquake (Figure 8, purple star)
382 detection shows that NYMAR can detect M_L 1.0 earthquakes at a hypocentral distance of 100
383 km. Further assessment of the detection capability and integrating the array into models of
384 seismic network detection capability (e.g., Möllhoff et al., 2019) is the subject of ongoing
385 work.

386 **5 Conclusion**

387 A dense array (NYMAR) has been deployed on the North York Moors, northeast England, UK,
388 to enhance regional earthquake detection and location capability in the Southern North Sea,
389 providing support for effective CO₂ storage monitoring operations. Data from NYMAR has
390 been used to baseline array performance using a simple array analysis implementation.
391 Detections have been compared to the wider UK seismicity catalogue, and small events ($M \sim 1$)
392 have been detected at significant distances ($r > 100$ km) from the array, demonstrating good
393 performance in comparison to the UK national seismic network. This is a similar performance
394 improvement as seen by Zarifi et al. (2023) for a dense array deployed to monitor the Northern
395 North Sea. Some small events, however, are not detected using the simple detection methods
396 employed in this first performance assessment. This could be due to variations in noise levels
397 at the time of the events, or radiation pattern effects reducing signal amplitude at the location
398 of the array. Future work, outside the scope of this study, aims to thoroughly investigate the
399 performance of the array using more sophisticated array analyses (e.g., Selby et al., 2008), and
400 determine if this number of detections can be improved. This data can be used as a resource for
401 regional earthquake monitoring, a baseline for technologies for offshore earthquake detection,
402 and a reference example for the use of dense seismic arrays.

403 **Acknowledgements**

404 This work was conducted as one of the UK National Environmental Research Council (NERC)
405 Agile Initiative Research Sprints (NERC grant reference number NE/W004976/1). Agile is one
406 of four Changing the Environment programmes funded by NERC.

407 **Data and code availability**

408 The continuous waveform data is available for the first year of NYMAR's deployment through
409 the National Geoscience Data Centre (NGDC), operated by the BGS. It can be found on the
410 NGDC here: **NGDC DOI TBC AS OF SEPT 2025**. Waveform data is also currently being
411 curated to be made available for download via FDSN client through the BGS EIDA node
412 (network code 3N), and is expected to be available in 2026. Figures in this work were produced
413 using Python Matplotlib and MATLAB 2025a, the code and data for which can be found on
414 Zenodo here: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183931.

415 **Competing interests**

416 The authors have no known competing interests, financial or otherwise, that would affect the
417 work reported in this manuscript.

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Supplementary Material for

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North York Moors Array (NYMAR) for enhancing regional background monitoring of
501 Southern North Sea CO₂ storage sites

502

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Supplementary Figure 1. Probabilistic power spectral density calculated for north-oriented horizontal

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component (HHN) data from each station in the North York Moors array, where signal amplitude is

511

plotted as a function of frequency, for data from 29th September 2023 to 29th September 2024. White

512

dashed lines show the 5 and 95 percentiles, and dark grey solid lines show the reference high and low

513

noise models for seismic stations (Peterson, 1993). The orange line shows a reference spectra for a M_L

514

1.5 earthquake at a hypocentral distance of 100 km (Clinton and Heaton, 2002).

515

516 **Supplementary Figure 2.** Probabilistic power spectral density calculated for north-oriented horizontal
 517 component (HHE) data from each station in the North York Moors array, where signal amplitude is
 518 plotted as a function of frequency, for data from 29th September 2023 to 29th September 2024. White
 519 dashed lines show the 5 and 95 percentiles, and dark grey solid lines show the reference high and low
 520 noise models for seismic stations (Peterson, 1993). The orange line shows a reference spectra for a M_L
 521 1.5 earthquake at a hypocentral distance of 100 km (Clinton and Heaton, 2002).

523

524 **Supplementary Figure 3.** Comparison between seismograms (left column) of the central station of the
 525 NYMAR array, NYM1, and the phase-weighted stack beam (right column) for a M_L 1.0 earthquake that
 526 occurred near the village of Kilnsey, Yorkshire (ca. 100 km from the array) recorded on April 10th,
 527 2024, at 04:36:37.4 UTC (Galloway, 2025). Waveforms shown are normalised with respect to the
 528 absolute maximum value on each component seismogram.